

Trade-off and Performance of Optoplasmonic Mesoporous WGM Sensors

Sadok Kouz^{1,*} and Abdel I. El Abed^{1,*}

¹Laboratoire Lumière Matière et Interfaces (LUMIN), UMR 9024, Ecole Normale Supérieure Paris Saclay, CentraleSupélec, CNRS, Université Paris-Saclay, 4 avenue des Sciences, 91190 Gif-sur-Yvette, France.

*Email: sadok.kouz@ens-paris-saclay.fr, abdel.el-abed@ens-paris-saclay.fr

Abstract

Optoplasmonic whispering-gallery-mode (WGM) sensors are often presented as a direct route to enhanced detection limits, because localized surface plasmon resonances can create extreme near-field intensities. However, for passive WGM refractometric sensing in porous resonators, plasmonic inclusions also introduce absorption that can strongly reduce the cavity quality factor and may negate any sensitivity gain. Here we develop a quantitative framework that builds on the Foreman–Vollmer T-matrix approach using a continuous-density approximation for volumetrically distributed nanoparticles (sum-to-integral replacement). We combine this with a two-step effective-medium model (Bruggeman + Maxwell–Garnett) to obtain the complex effective refractive index of the nanoparticle-doped mesoporous shell. This enables a direct evaluation of the trade-off between refractive-index sensitivity and absorption-induced Q degradation through the figure of merit $FOM = SQ_{\text{total}}$. For passive, visible-wavelength operation at 645 nm, we find that any nonzero volumetric loading degrades the refractometric FOM relative to the bare mesoporous resonator: for gold nanoparticles, the best-performing doped case in our sweep occurs at the smallest nonzero fraction considered ($f = 10^{-3}$) and still reduces the FOM by 41%, while silver yields a smaller but still negative change (13%). Beyond equilibrium performance, we couple the optical model to hindered diffusion in the porous network and show that nanoparticle loading can imprint temporal signatures that encode transport and binding kinetics. These results establish a practical design rule for hollow mesoporous WGM refractometric sensors in the visible range: plasmonic *doping* does not improve the passive-cavity FOM, and the bare sensor remains optimal unless time-resolved kinetic fingerprinting (or an active/gain-compensated architecture) is the primary goal.

Keywords

whispering gallery modes, hollow mesoporous silica, plasmonic nanoparticles, effective medium theory, refractometric sensing, quality factor degradation, figure of merit.

Schematic illustration of the trade-off in volumetric optoplasmonic sensors: plasmonic doping increases sensitivity/overlap (green, $S \uparrow$) but reduces quality factor (red, $Q \downarrow$), leading to a net degradation of the figure of merit $FOM = S \times Q$ in passive cavities.

1 Introduction

Whispering-gallery-mode (WGM) microresonators are widely used for label-free refractometric sensing since small perturbations of the local dielectric environment translate into measurable resonance shifts and linewidth changes. [1–3] To push these sensors toward single-entity detection, plasmonic nanoparticles are often introduced to create the so-called optoplasmonic resonators in which a WGM excites a localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) and thereby concentrates the optical field into nanoscale hotspots. [4–6] In this hybrid architecture, the large near-field gradients associated with an LSPR can strongly enhance the perturbation induced by a binding event and enable single-molecule or single-nanoparticle readout based on reactive sensing mechanisms. [5–7] Recent perspectives highlight how this "few-antenna" optoplasmonic paradigm (typically nanorods positioned at the WGM rim) enables a rich set of single-entity modalities, including conformational dynamics, thermo-optoplasmonic sensing, and active (microlaser) readout schemes. [8–11]

Mesoporous WGM resonators provide a qualitatively different scenario. First, the relevant interaction volume is not limited to a 2D surface: a mesoporous shell provides internal surface area and pore space that can, in principle, host a *volumetric* distribution of plasmonic inclusions and analyte molecules. Second, mass transport is no longer purely "bulk-to-surface"; analytes may need to diffuse through a tortuous

porous network, which can generate time-dependent signatures that couple transport kinetics to the optical response. These two aspects suggest a natural hypothesis: infiltrating a mesoporous WGM shell with plasmonic nanoparticles could create a volumetric distribution of hotspots and thereby increase the total interaction strength compared with conventional surface-decorated optoplasmonic geometries.

A central limitation, however, is that plasmonic enhancement is inseparable from absorption and scattering losses [12–14]. For passive refractometric sensors, the relevant figure of merit that captures this trade-off is given by the quantity $\text{FOM} = S \times Q$, where $S = \partial\lambda/\partial n$ is the sensitivity (wavelength shift per refractive index change) and Q is the quality factor of the resonator. A high FOM requires both strong sensitivity and narrow linewidth (high Q). As a consequence, it is not obvious *a priori* whether the net FOM improves or degrades once plasmonic nanostructures are introduced into a given cavity platform: while they may increase S through field enhancement, they simultaneously reduce Q through absorption, and the net effect depends on the balance between these two effects [12, 14]. The trade-off is particularly acute for *passive-cavity* refractometric sensing, where added loss directly reduces Q and thus the attainable resolution—unlike in active or gain-compensated cavities, where loss can be offset [12, 14]. Moreover, most existing optoplasmonic theoretical descriptions and design intuitions are developed for geometries in which nanoparticles are placed on (or near) a smooth solid interface, rather than distributed throughout a 3D porous scaffold. [5]

This work is motivated by our recent microfluidic fabrication and optical characterization of highly monodisperse mesoporous hollow silica microcapsules supporting robust WGMs. [15] That experimental platform provides a physically realized geometry—including shell thickness, porosity, and optical operating conditions—in which “volumetric optoplasmonics” becomes a realistic design direction rather than a purely conceptual one. [15] At the same time, it raises a concrete and practically relevant question that is distinct from reactive single-entity optoplasmonics: Under *passive-cavity refractometric* operation, does the sensitivity enhancement from volumetric plasmonic doping outweigh the accompanying absorption-induced Q degradation—or does the net figure of merit $\text{FOM} = S \times Q$ ultimately degrade?

To address this question, we develop a quantitative theoretical framework for volumetric optoplasmonic sensing in mesoporous WGM resonators. We build on the Foreman–Vollmer T-matrix approach [5] and introduce a continuous-density (sum-to-integral) approximation for nanoparticles distributed throughout the mesoporous shell volume, which allows us to treat volumetric rather than surface-only nanoparticle configurations within a unified formalism. We then combine this optical coupling picture with a two-step effective-medium model (Bruggeman for the porous silica host followed by Maxwell–Garnett for dilute plasmonic inclusions) to compute the complex effective refractive index of the nanoparticle-doped porous composite, including absorption losses. [16–19] With these ingredients, we quantify the competition between (i) the geometric/field-overlap enhancement enabled by volumetric loading and (ii) the absorption-driven reduction

in cavity Q , and we evaluate the resulting impact on the passive refractometric figure of merit under realistic parameters informed by our mesoporous hollow silica microcapsule [15].

Finally, we outline how the optical model couples to hindered diffusion in the porous network, showing that nanoparticle loading can imprint time-dependent WGM signatures that encode transport and binding kinetics (detailed in the Supplementary Material) [11].

2 Theoretical Model

2.1 Effective Medium for Plasmonic-Doped Porous Silica

We consider a hollow spherical microcapsule with an outer radius R and a mesoporous shell thickness t (with $t \ll R$), as characterized in our previous work [15]. The hollow core is filled with the same fluid medium as the pores, ensuring refractive index matching and simplifying the WGM boundary conditions. The shell porosity $\phi = 0.63$ is taken from experimental BET measurements. The pores are initially filled with a medium of refractive index $n_{\text{pore}} = 1.33$ (water). We then introduce a small volume fraction f of gold nanoparticles (spherical, with a radius of $a = 10$ nm) uniformly distributed within the pores. For numerical calculations, we use the experimentally determined values of $R = 44 \mu\text{m}$ and $t = 5 \mu\text{m}$ from Ref. [15].

To obtain the effective optical properties of this three-component mixture (silica matrix, pore fluid, and nanoparticles), we use a two-step homogenization procedure [16–21]. This approach accounts for the different length scales involved: the pores are much larger than the nanoparticles, but both are much smaller than the optical wavelength. A detailed pedagogical derivation is provided in the Supporting Information.

1. **Bruggeman model for empty pores:** First, we homogenize the porous silica scaffold (refractive index $n_{\text{SiO}_2} = 1.47$) with the pore fluid ($n_{\text{pore}} = 1.33$) to obtain an intermediate effective index $n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}}$. This represents the refractive index of the fluid-filled porous matrix *without* nanoparticles. The Bruggeman equation,

$$(1 - \phi) \frac{n_{\text{SiO}_2}^2 - (n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}})^2}{n_{\text{SiO}_2}^2 + 2(n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}})^2} + \phi \frac{n_{\text{pore}}^2 - (n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}})^2}{n_{\text{pore}}^2 + 2(n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}})^2} = 0, \quad (1)$$

yields $n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}} \approx 1.38$ for our parameters.

2. **Maxwell-Garnett for nanoparticle inclusions:** Next, we treat the gold nanoparticles (complex permittivity $\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda)$) as dilute inclusions embedded in a host medium with permittivity $\varepsilon_{\text{pore}} = (n_{\text{pore}}^{\text{eff}})^2$. For low filling fractions $f \ll 1$, the Maxwell–Garnett formula gives the effective permittivity ε_{eff} of the

composite:

$$\frac{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}} - \varepsilon_{\text{pore}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}} + 2\varepsilon_{\text{pore}}} = f \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{np}} - \varepsilon_{\text{pore}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{np}} + 2\varepsilon_{\text{pore}}}. \quad (2)$$

The complex effective refractive index of the doped shell is then $\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}}$. Its real part $n_{\text{eff}} = \text{Re}(\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}})$ determines the WGM resonance wavelengths, while its imaginary part $\kappa = \text{Im}(\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}})$ quantifies optical absorption and directly impacts the quality factor Q .

2.2 Optical constants of gold and silver

The complex dielectric functions of gold and silver were modeled using the Drude–Lorentz (DL) oscillator model parameterized by Rakić *et al.* [22]. These parameters accurately reproduce the experimental data of Johnson and Christy [23] over the 450–900 nm wavelength range. For gold, the Drude term is characterized by a plasma energy $\hbar\omega_p = 9.03$ eV, an oscillator strength $f_0 = 0.760$, and a damping constant $\Gamma_0 = 0.053$ eV. Five Lorentz oscillators account for interband transitions, with parameters $(f_j, \Gamma_j, \omega_j)$ taken from Table I of Ref. [22]. The same functional form was used for silver, with its corresponding DL parameters (see Supplementary Material for the full set of coefficients).

For a given wavelength λ , the complex permittivity of the metal $\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda)$ is computed, and the effective permittivity ε_{eff} of the nanoparticle-doped porous composite is obtained via the two-step homogenization described in Sect. 2.1. The complex effective refractive index $\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{\text{eff}}}$ is then evaluated. To ensure a physically meaningful result for a passive medium, we enforce the condition $\text{Im}(\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}}) \geq 0$; if the principal square root yields a negative imaginary part, we take the opposite branch ($\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}} \leftarrow -\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}}$). A final numerical safeguard sets $\kappa = \text{Im}(\tilde{n}_{\text{eff}})$ to zero if it remains negative due to floating-point errors. This branch selection guaranties that the extinction coefficient κ is non-negative, as required for a causal, lossy material.

2.3 Coupled WGM–LSPR System

Following the T-matrix approach of Foreman and Vollmer [5], the resonance condition for a WGM of order l and azimuthal number m interacting with a distribution of small scatterers (nanoparticles) at positions \mathbf{r}_j is given by

$$0 = \frac{1}{\eta_l'} \frac{1}{\kappa_1^E} - \sum_j \mathcal{U}_{lm}^{1m}(\mathbf{r}_j) \tilde{\mathcal{U}}_{1m}^{lm}(\mathbf{r}_j), \quad (3)$$

where η_l' and κ_1^E relate to the isolated WGM and LSPR poles, respectively, and \mathcal{U} are coupling coefficients depending on the field overlap and nanoparticle polarizability.

For a continuous distribution of nanoparticles within the mesoporous shell, we replace the discrete sum

by an integral over the shell volume V_{shell} :

$$\sum_j \longrightarrow \int_{V_{\text{shell}}} \rho(\mathbf{r}) d^3r, \quad (4)$$

with $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ the nanoparticle number density. This continuous-density replacement is justified in the dilute-inclusion regime ($f \ll 1$), where inter-particle electromagnetic coupling and multiple scattering are negligible, and the total perturbation can be approximated as a superposition of independent single-particle contributions. This assumption is consistent with the Maxwell–Garnett effective-medium theory used later.

Assuming a uniform density ρ_0 and that the spatial variation of the WGM field is small over the typical inter-particle distance, we obtain an approximate expression for the resonance wavelength shift:

$$\Delta\lambda \approx \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi n_{\text{eff}} R} \cdot \frac{\alpha_{\text{np}} \int_{\text{shell}} |E(\mathbf{r})|^2 \rho_0 dV}{\int_{\text{total}} |E(\mathbf{r})|^2 dV}, \quad (5)$$

where α_{np} is the (complex) polarizability of a single nanoparticle, and $|E|^2$ is the WGM intensity profile.

To reveal the resonant nature of the plasmonic enhancement, we recall that for a small spherical nanoparticle of radius a in the dipole approximation, the polarizability is

$$\alpha_{\text{np}}(\lambda) = 4\pi a^3 \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda) - \varepsilon_{\text{host}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda) + 2\varepsilon_{\text{host}}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda)$ is the complex permittivity of the metal and $\varepsilon_{\text{host}}$ is that of the surrounding medium (the pore fluid). The denominator $\varepsilon_{\text{np}} + 2\varepsilon_{\text{host}}$ vanishes at the LSPR wavelength, causing a resonant enhancement of α_{np} . We therefore define a dimensionless **plasmonic enhancement factor**

$$\Gamma_{\text{LSPR}}(\lambda) = \left| \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda) - \varepsilon_{\text{host}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{np}}(\lambda) + 2\varepsilon_{\text{host}}} \right|, \quad (7)$$

so that $\alpha_{\text{np}} = 4\pi a^3 \Gamma_{\text{LSPR}} e^{i\phi}$ (the phase ϕ accounts for the complex nature). Substituting into Eq. (5) gives

$$\Delta\lambda \approx \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi n_{\text{eff}} R} \cdot \frac{4\pi a^3 \Gamma_{\text{LSPR}} \int_{\text{shell}} |E|^2 \rho_0 dV}{\int_{\text{total}} |E|^2 dV}. \quad (8)$$

This form makes explicit that the WGM shift scales with the nanoparticle volume a^3 , the nanoparticle density ρ_0 , and the resonant enhancement factor Γ_{LSPR} . The combination $\rho_0 \alpha_{\text{np}}$ can be interpreted as an effective plasmonic susceptibility of the composite shell, providing a natural link to the effective-medium

description developed in the following section.

2.4 Volumetric Enhancement Factor

We define the enhancement factor \mathcal{E} as the ratio of the shift for the volumetric distribution to that of a single optimally placed nanoparticle on the surface:

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{\int_{\text{shell}} |E|^2 \rho_0 dV}{|E_{\text{max}}|^2}, \quad (9)$$

where $|E_{\text{max}}|^2$ is the maximum field intensity at the WGM antinode on the outer surface.

For a WGM confined near the outer surface, the field decays exponentially into the shell: $|E(r)|^2 \approx |E_0|^2 e^{-2(r-R)/\delta}$, with a penetration depth of $\delta \sim \lambda/(2\pi\sqrt{n_{\text{eff}}^2 - 1}) \approx 100$ nm and $|E_0|^2 = |E(R)|^2$. For a shell thickness $t \gg \delta$, the integral over the shell volume becomes

$$\int_{\text{shell}} |E|^2 dV \approx |E_0|^2 \cdot 4\pi R^2 \cdot \frac{\delta}{2}. \quad (10)$$

The number density ρ_0 is related to the nanoparticle volume fraction f (within the pores) by $\rho_0 = f/V_{\text{np}}$, where $V_{\text{np}} = \frac{4}{3}\pi a^3$ is the volume of a single nanoparticle of radius a . Substituting into Eq. (9) and taking $|E_{\text{max}}|^2 = |E_0|^2$ gives

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{f}{\frac{4}{3}\pi a^3} \cdot 4\pi R^2 \cdot \frac{\delta}{2} = \frac{3fR^2\delta}{2a^3}. \quad (11)$$

This expression makes explicit that the enhancement factor depends on the nanoparticle radius a . For fixed volume fraction f , smaller nanoparticles yield a larger \mathcal{E} because more particles contribute to the total field overlap. The single-particle shift itself scales as a^3 , so the product $\alpha_{\text{np}}\rho_0$ —and hence the total shift—is independent of a , as expected.

For the typical parameters used in this work ($a = 10$ nm, $R = 44$ μm , $\delta = 0.1$ μm), Eq. (11) yields $\mathcal{E} \approx 2.9 \times 10^8 f$. Thus even for volume fractions as low as $f \sim 10^{-8}$, the enhancement factor can reach values of order unity, and for $f = 0.01$ it becomes extremely large ($\mathcal{E} \sim 3 \times 10^6$). This represents a dramatic increase in total interaction compared to a single surface nanoparticle.

However, \mathcal{E} quantifies only the geometric/overlap amplification of the wavelength shift and does not include the absorption-driven reduction of Q introduced by the same nanoparticles; therefore, the net impact on passive refractometric performance requires a figure of merit that combines sensitivity and Q , which we evaluate in Sect. 3.

2.5 Loss Mechanisms and Q-Factor Degradation

The presence of absorbing nanoparticles introduces additional loss channels that reduce the quality factor of the resonator. To understand this effect quantitatively, we first recall the definition of the quality factor Q .

For any resonant mode,

$$Q = \frac{2\pi \times \text{Energy stored in the mode}}{\text{Energy lost per optical cycle}}. \quad (12)$$

For a mode with angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi c/\lambda$, the energy loss per cycle is related to the absorption coefficient α (in m^{-1}). When absorption dominates, α is linked to the imaginary part of the refractive index, κ , by

$$\alpha = \frac{4\pi\kappa}{\lambda}, \quad (13)$$

and the corresponding absorption-limited quality factor is

$$Q_{\text{abs}} = \frac{2\pi n_{\text{eff}}}{\alpha\lambda} = \frac{n_{\text{eff}}}{2\kappa}. \quad (14)$$

Notice that λ cancels; the expression depends only on the real index n_{eff} and the extinction coefficient κ .

For the bare, undoped shell ($f = 0$), the experimentally determined quality factor is $Q_0 = 1000$ (from Ref. [15]). This value already includes all loss channels present without nanoparticles: scattering from the porous structure (Q_{scatt}), absorption by the Rhodamine B dye ($Q_{\text{abs,dye}}$), and radiative losses (Q_{rad}). In terms of an effective extinction coefficient, these background losses correspond to κ_0 , obtained from the effective-medium model at $f = 0$:

$$Q_0 = \frac{n_{\text{eff}}(f = 0)}{2\kappa_0}. \quad (15)$$

When nanoparticles are introduced ($f > 0$), the total extinction coefficient κ_{total} computed from the effective-medium model (Eq. (2)) includes both the background absorption and the additional nanoparticle absorption. The contribution solely due to the nanoparticles is therefore

$$\kappa_{\text{nano}} = \kappa_{\text{total}} - \kappa_0. \quad (16)$$

The associated absorption-limited quality factor for the nanoparticles alone is then

$$Q_{\text{abs,nano}} = \frac{n_{\text{eff}}}{2\kappa_{\text{nano}}}. \quad (17)$$

Because the background losses are already accounted for in Q_0 , the total quality factor of the doped shell

is obtained by adding the nanoparticle loss channel in parallel with the intrinsic cavity loss:

$$\frac{1}{Q_{\text{total}}} = \frac{1}{Q_0} + \frac{1}{Q_{\text{abs,nano}}}. \quad (18)$$

This formulation ensures that the nanoparticle contribution is not double-counted with the background absorption already present in the bare resonator.

Balance Between Geometric Enhancement and Q-Degradation

It is crucial to note that Eq. (11) quantifies only the geometric enhancement of the field overlap integral—that is, the increase in the numerator of Eq. (5) due to volumetric loading. This factor alone would suggest that adding nanoparticles always improves sensitivity. However, it completely neglects the accompanying reduction in quality factor Q_{total} caused by nanoparticle absorption. The effective sensor performance is captured by the figure of merit

$$\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}, \quad (19)$$

where the sensitivity $S = \partial\lambda/\partial n_{\text{pore}}$ is obtained via the chain rule:

$$S = \frac{\lambda}{n_{\text{eff}}} \cdot \frac{dn_{\text{eff}}}{dn_{\text{pore}}}. \quad (20)$$

where the total derivative reflects that n_{eff} is solely a function of n_{pore} via the effective medium.

The FOM therefore quantifies this trade-off: volumetric loading increases S (by raising $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$) but decreases Q_{total} (by introducing absorption). As we will demonstrate in Section 3.3, the loss-induced Q-degradation dominates for spherical gold nanoparticles, leading to a net decrease in FOM even at the smallest loadings. This trade-off is the central finding of the present study.

3 Numerical Results and Discussion

3.1 Effective Optical Properties vs. Nanoparticle Loading

We implemented the two-step homogenization in MATLAB for a wavelength of $\lambda = 645$ nm (the peak of the Rhodamine B fluorescence used in our experiments). Figure 1 shows the real part n_{eff} and the extinction coefficient κ as functions of the nanoparticle volume fraction f inside the mesoporous shell.

As f increases from 0 to 0.1, n_{eff} rises slowly from 1.381 to 1.746, a relative increase of about 26%. This modest change reflects the fact that the gold nanoparticles ($n \approx 0.15 + 3.5i$ at 645 nm) have a real

Figure 1: (a) Real part of the effective refractive index n_{eff} and (b) extinction coefficient κ versus nanoparticle volume fraction f , computed at $\lambda = 645$ nm for $\phi = 0.63$, $n_{\text{pore}} = 1.33$. Our physical interpretation is restricted to $f \lesssim 10^{-2}$, as the Maxwell–Garnett approximation becomes questionable at higher loadings.

permittivity smaller than that of silica, so they do not dramatically alter the average polarizability of the composite. In contrast, the extinction coefficient κ grows much more steeply, from effectively zero at $f = 0$ to 9.75×10^{-3} at $f = 0.1$. This sharp increase directly reflects the strong absorption of gold at visible wavelengths, where interband transitions contribute significantly to the imaginary part of the permittivity [23–25]. As we will see in Section 3.3, this rise in κ is the dominant factor limiting the quality factor and, consequently, the overall sensor performance.

3.2 Sensitivity factor and Convergence

The sensitivity factor $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ quantifies how effectively changes in the pore fluid refractive index are transduced into changes in the effective index of the composite shell. This factor was computed numerically using a finite difference with perturbation $\Delta n_{\text{pore}} = 0.01$. To ensure the accuracy of our numerical differentiation, we performed a rigorous validation using two complementary approaches.

First, we derived an analytical expression for $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ at $f = 0$ by implicit differentiation of the Bruggeman equation (see Supplementary Material for the full derivation). This analytical value is 0.638. To validate our numerical approach, we computed the derivative at $f = 0$ using successively smaller step sizes Δn_{pore} , ranging from 10^{-1} down to 10^{-5} . As shown in Table 1, the numerical values converge rapidly to the analytical result, with the error decreasing monotonically. Even with the relatively coarse step $\Delta n_{\text{pore}} = 0.01$ used throughout this work, the relative error is only 0.05%, which is more than adequate for our analysis.

Second, we verified the convergence for a representative non-zero loading, $f = 0.02$. The difference

Table 1: Convergence of the numerical derivative $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ at $f = 0$ as a function of step size Δn_{pore} . The analytical value is 0.638530.

Δn_{pore}	Numerical derivative	Relative error
1.0×10^{-1}	0.635261	5.12×10^{-3}
1.0×10^{-2}	0.638183	5.43×10^{-4}
1.0×10^{-3}	0.638495	5.48×10^{-5}
1.0×10^{-4}	0.638526	6.26×10^{-6}
1.0×10^{-5}	0.638529	1.57×10^{-6}

between the derivatives computed with $\Delta n_{\text{pore}} = 10^{-4}$ and 10^{-5} is only 2.18×10^{-7} , confirming that the numerical scheme is fully converged and that our chosen step size $\Delta n_{\text{pore}} = 0.01$ introduces negligible error. This rigorous validation ensures that the sensitivity factors reported below are numerically accurate to better than 0.1%.

Figure 2 displays $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ as a function of f . The factor increases monotonically from 0.6382 at $f = 0$ to 0.6417 at the optimal loading $f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$ (the smallest non-zero f in our sweep), and further to 1.0166 at $f = 0.1$. Several important observations follow from these results:

- At very low loadings ($f \lesssim 0.01$), the increase in sensitivity is extremely modest—only about 0.5% at $f = 0.0010$. This is because the nanoparticles are sparse and their contribution to the effective polarizability is small compared to the silica matrix and pore fluid.
- At higher loadings ($f > 0.02$), the derivative increases more rapidly, reflecting the growing influence of the nanoparticle polarizability as they begin to constitute a significant volume fraction of the composite.
- The fact that $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ continues to increase even at the highest loadings confirms that nanoparticle doping does enhance the refractive-index response of the pore fluid. This enhancement is a necessary condition for any potential sensitivity improvement.

Crucially, the small magnitude of the increase at low f will prove decisive when we combine it with the quality factor degradation in the next section. Even a modest improvement in sensitivity is insufficient to offset the dramatic drop in Q caused by nanoparticle absorption, leading to the net performance degradation that is the central finding of this work.

3.3 Figure of Merit and Optimal Loading

Combining the sensitivity $S = (\lambda/n_{\text{eff}}) \times (dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}})$ with the total quality factor Q_{total} (which includes the intrinsic $Q_0 = 1000$ and the absorption-limited $Q_{\text{abs,nano}} = n_{\text{eff}}/(2\kappa)$), we computed the figure of merit $\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$. Figure 3 shows the FOM as a function of f , including the bare sensor at $f = 0$.

Figure 2: Derivative $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ versus nanoparticle volume fraction f . The monotonic increase confirms that nanoparticle doping enhances the sensitivity of the effective index to changes in the pore fluid. The increase is very gradual at low f (inset), becoming more pronounced only at higher loadings. Our physical interpretation is restricted to $f \lesssim 10^{-2}$, as the Maxwell-Garnett approximation becomes questionable at higher loadings.

Figure 3: Comparison of the figure of merit $\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$ for gold and silver nanoparticles as a function of volume fraction f . Both metals degrade performance relative to the bare sensor ($f = 0$), with silver showing a smaller reduction (12.9% at $f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$) than gold (40.5% at the same loading). Our physical interpretation is restricted to $f \lesssim 10^{-2}$, as the Maxwell-Garnett approximation becomes questionable at higher loadings.

The bare sensor exhibits the highest overall FOM (2.98×10^5 nm/RIU). For any finite loading $f > 0$, the FOM drops immediately. Within the set of doped sensors, the optimum is found at the smallest non-zero f considered; with our 100-point sweep this is $f = 0.0010$, yielding FOM = 1.77×10^5 nm/RIU for gold (see Section 3.5 for silver). A higher-resolution sweep (10,000 points) gives an even smaller optimal loading (e.g., $f \approx 10^{-5}$) with an FOM of 2.66×10^5 nm/RIU (essentially unchanged) and confirms that the FOM increases monotonically as f decreases, always remaining below the bare-sensor value. This demonstrates that the performance degradation is unavoidable: the bare sensor remains the optimal configuration for this platform.

3.4 Spectral dependence of the figure of merit

To assess whether the detrimental effect of plasmonic nanoparticles persists across a broader wavelength range, we computed the figure of merit $\text{FOM}(\lambda) = S(\lambda) \times Q_{\text{total}}(\lambda)$ from 450 to 900 nm for several representative loadings (Fig. 4). For the bare sensor ($f = 0$), the FOM increases monotonically with wavelength, reflecting the λ/n_{eff} scaling of the sensitivity. Introducing gold nanoparticles reduces the FOM at all wavelengths, but the degradation is strongly wavelength-dependent.

In the visible region (450–700 nm), where interband transitions render gold highly absorptive, even a moderate loading of $f = 10^{-3}$ causes a noticeable drop in FOM (up to 29% at 450 nm). Higher loadings ($f = 10^{-2}$) lead to a catastrophic collapse (80% loss at 450 nm). These results confirm that for visible-light operation, any finite loading of plasmonic nanoparticles reduces the figure of merit relative to the bare sensor.

In the near-infrared (700–900 nm), the absorption losses weaken, and the FOM for $f = 10^{-3}$ approaches that of the bare resonator (within 3.5% at 900 nm). For $f = 10^{-2}$, however, the degradation remains substantial (24% loss at 900 nm). This indicates that while ultra-low loadings ($f \lesssim 10^{-3}$) might be tolerated in the NIR without major penalty, any loading sufficient to provide a measurable plasmonic enhancement (typically $f > 10^{-3}$) still compromises the sensor performance. The bare silica resonator therefore remains the optimal choice for refractometric sensing across the entire visible spectrum, and even in the NIR the margin for beneficial doping is extremely narrow.

At the highest loading ($f = 10^{-1}$), numerical instabilities and branch-selection issues in the complex square root can yield unphysical values (e.g., negative κ and thus negative Q_{abs}). In practice, such large metal volume fractions are also outside the dilute-inclusion regime where Maxwell–Garnett homogenization is reliable, and would strongly damp or suppress well-defined WGMs. Therefore, we restrict our physical interpretation to the dilute regime ($f \lesssim 10^{-2}$), which is the relevant range for nanoparticle-doped mesoporous shells.

Figure 4: Figure of merit $FOM = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$ as a function of wavelength for different gold nanoparticle volume fractions f in a mesoporous silica matrix (left axis). The bare sensor ($f = 0$) shows the highest FOM across the entire spectrum. The black solid line (right axis) shows the absorption coefficient $\alpha = 4\pi\kappa/\lambda$ (see Eq. 13) for $f = 10^{-4}$, illustrating that the minimum FOM coincides with the maximum plasmonic absorption of the nanoparticles.

This spectral analysis reveals that gold’s strong absorption in the visible—particularly near its interband transition threshold—is responsible for the FOM degradation. If this mechanism is correct, then a metal with a higher interband threshold, such as silver, should exhibit a smaller but still measurable degradation at 645 nm. We test this prediction next.

3.5 Comparison with Silver Nanoparticles

To test whether the performance degradation observed for gold is specific to that metal or a more general phenomenon, we repeated the analysis for silver nanoparticles. Silver is often considered superior for plasmonic applications because its intrinsic losses are lower in the near-infrared, and its Drude damping constant is smaller [22, 23]. However, at visible wavelengths, interband transitions can also contribute to absorption, though their onset is at higher energies than for gold [12, 14]. Figure 3 compares the figure of merit $FOM = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$ for gold and silver as functions of the nanoparticle volume fraction f .

At our operating wavelength $\lambda = 645$ nm, silver consistently yields a higher FOM than gold for any finite loading $f > 0$. The optimal loading remains $f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$, with a maximum FOM for silver of 2.60×10^5 nm/RIU, corresponding to a reduction of 12.9% relative to the bare sensor, compared to a 40.5% reduction

for gold at the same loading. The superior performance of silver across all loadings is consistent with its lower intrinsic loss at this wavelength. Silver’s interband transitions lie at higher energies (threshold near 3.9 eV, ~ 318 nm), leaving the 645 nm region dominated by the Drude contribution with relatively low loss. Gold, in contrast, has an interband threshold near 1.8 eV (~ 689 nm), placing our wavelength just above that edge, where absorption remains significant [23].

Thus, while both metals degrade the figure of merit relative to the bare sensor, silver is less detrimental at visible wavelengths. This result underscores that the degradation is not simply a matter of choosing a "better" metal; rather, it reflects the fundamental trade-off between field enhancement and absorption that is inherent to all plasmonic materials [4, 12, 14]. The only potential exceptions would require operation in the near-infrared (where both metals exhibit much lower absorption) or the use of non-metallic high-index nanoparticles (e.g., silicon, germanium) that achieve strong field confinement without Ohmic losses.

To further illustrate the wavelength dependence of this degradation, Fig. 5 shows the FOM as a function of wavelength for several silver loadings, along with the absorption spectrum of the nanoparticles. The absorption peak of silver near 350 nm causes a sharp drop in FOM, confirming that the performance loss is directly linked to the plasmonic absorption.

This generality strengthens our central conclusion: for mesoporous WGM sensors operating at visible wavelengths, plasmonic doping consistently degrades the figure of merit. The bare sensor ($f = 0$) remains the optimal configuration for biosensing applications.

3.6 Comparison with a high-index matrix (TiO₂)

To assess whether the performance degradation observed for silica is specific to its relatively low refractive index, we repeated our analysis for a hypothetical mesoporous titania (TiO₂, $n \approx 2.6$) matrix, keeping all other parameters identical ($\phi = 0.63$, $Q_0 = 1000$, $\lambda = 645$ nm). Table 2 summarizes the key quantities at zero loading and at the optimal nanoparticle fraction $f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$, and Fig. 6 shows the quality factor, sensitivity factor, and FOM as functions of f for both materials. We emphasize that using the same Q_0 for both matrices isolates the *plasmonic absorption penalty* predicted by the effective-medium model; in practice Q_0 may differ between materials depending on scattering, crystallinity, and fabrication quality.

Several important observations emerge from this comparison. First, the bare TiO₂ resonator exhibits a **lower baseline FOM** than its silica counterpart, despite its higher refractive index (Fig. 6c). This counterintuitive result stems from the tighter confinement of the WGM field inside the high-index skeleton, which reduces the evanescent overlap with the pore fluid and consequently lowers the sensitivity $S = (\lambda/n_{\text{eff}}) \times (dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}})$. Although the factor $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ is slightly larger for TiO₂ (0.715 vs. 0.638,

Figure 5: Figure of merit $FOM = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$ as a function of wavelength for different silver nanoparticle volume fractions f in a mesoporous silica matrix (left axis). The bare sensor ($f = 0$) shows the highest FOM across the entire spectrum. The black solid line (right axis) shows the absorption coefficient $\alpha = 4\pi\kappa/\lambda$ for $f = 10^{-4}$, illustrating that the minimum FOM coincides with the maximum plasmonic absorption of the silver nanoparticles.

Table 2: Comparison of key sensor parameters for SiO_2 and TiO_2 mesoporous matrices at $\lambda = 645$ nm, $\phi = 0.63$, and $Q_0 = 1000$. The optimal loading is $f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$ for both materials.

Quantity (at $f = 0$ unless stated)	SiO_2	TiO_2
Effective index n_{eff}	1.381	1.759
Sensitivity factor $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$	0.6382	0.7151
Extinction coefficient κ at $f = 0.1$	5.49×10^{-2}	2.77×10^{-1}
FOM_0 (10^3 nm/RIU)	298.0	262.3
FOM_{opt} (10^3 nm/RIU)	176.4	77.1
Relative degradation at f_{opt}	-40.8%	-70.6%

Fig. 6b), this increase is outweighed by the larger n_{eff} in the denominator of the prefactor λ/n_{eff} .

Second, upon introduction of plasmonic nanoparticles, the degradation of the FOM is **dramatically more severe for TiO₂** (70.6% loss at f_{opt}) than for SiO₂ (40.8% loss). As shown in Fig. 6(a), the quality factor collapses far more rapidly for TiO₂, since the effective-medium model yields a substantially larger composite extinction coefficient κ for Au inclusions in a high-index host at the same volume fraction, and the absorption-limited quality factor scales as $Q_{\text{abs}} = n_{\text{eff}}/(2\kappa)$. Although the sensitivity factor $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$ increases more rapidly with loading for TiO₂ (reaching 1.72 at $f = 0.1$, vs. 1.13 for SiO₂, Fig. 6b), this gain is completely overwhelmed by the larger rise in κ . This further illustrates that absorption losses, not insufficient sensitivity enhancement, are the dominant mechanism behind the performance degradation. These results indicate that moving to a high-index dielectric does not alleviate—and in fact worsens—the performance degradation caused by plasmonic doping.

Interestingly, the strong increase in κ predicted for TiO₂-Au composites is precisely what makes such hybrids attractive beyond the sensing context. When light absorption—rather than resonance sharpness—is the figure of merit, the same plasmonic loading that catastrophically degrades Q becomes a powerful design lever. This is not merely a theoretical prediction: WGM-assisted plasmonic absorption in Au/TiO₂ microspheres has been experimentally demonstrated to enhance visible-light absorption by over an order of magnitude relative to bare TiO₂, a direct consequence of the resonant field amplification at WGM wavelengths that we quantify here through the effective-medium extinction coefficient κ . [26, 27]

Specifically, Zhang et al. showed that engineering the Au nanoparticle distribution on TiO₂ microspheres acting as WGM cavities yields a broadband visible absorption enhancement that directly boosts photocatalytic water-splitting efficiency—a goal for which a high κ is desirable and Q -degradation is irrelevant. [26] Similarly, Xin *et al.* demonstrated that TiO₂/Au/TiO₂ heterostructures exploiting WGM resonance assistance achieve dramatically enhanced plasmonic photocatalysis, confirming that the WGM-LSPR coupling responsible for the absorption increase is the same mechanism that, in a passive-cavity refractometric context, degrades performance. [27] This contrast highlights a **fundamental design dichotomy**: the very physical mechanism—increased composite κ driven by plasmonic absorption—that is detrimental for high-resolution passive refractometry is precisely the resource exploited in photocatalytic and photothermal applications. Our effective-medium framework therefore provides a unified quantitative basis for both conclusions: the same two-step homogenization that predicts FOM degradation for sensing also predicts the absorption enhancement for photocatalysis, simply by evaluating $\text{Im}(n_{\text{eff}})$ rather than $S \times Q_{\text{total}}$ as the relevant figure of merit.

Comparison of mesoporous SiO_2 and TiO_2 matrices under gold nanoparticle loading

Figure 6: Comparison of mesoporous SiO_2 and TiO_2 matrices under gold nanoparticle loading versus volume fraction f . **(a)** Total quality factor Q_{total} . **(b)** Sensitivity factor $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$. **(c)** Figure of merit $\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$; symbols mark $f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$ for both matrices. Our physical interpretation is restricted to $f \lesssim 10^{-2}$, as the Maxwell–Garnett approximation becomes questionable at higher loadings.

3.7 Robustness Analysis

The results above establish that plasmonic doping degrades the FOM for silica and TiO_2 matrices under our baseline parameters ($Q_0 = 1000$, $\phi = 0.63$). To verify that this conclusion is not an artifact of these specific choices, we examined the FOM across a wide range of intrinsic quality factors ($Q_0 = 500$ to 5000) and porosities ($\phi = 0.5$ to 0.75). Table 3 demonstrates that in every case, $\text{FOM}(f = 0)$ exceeds the figure of merit for any finite loading $f > 0$, confirming that the bare sensor remains optimal regardless of these parameter variations.

3.8 Discussion and Design Guidelines

Our analysis reveals a counterintuitive but practically important result: for *passive* porous-shell WGM refractometric sensing in the visible, volumetric plasmonic doping does not increase the performance figure of merit $\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$. Although nanoparticle loading increases the refractive-index response of the

Table 3: Robustness check: figure of merit (nm/RIU) for different Q_0 and porosity ϕ at selected volume fractions f . In all cases $\text{FOM}(f = 0) > \text{FOM}(f > 0)$.

Q_0	ϕ	$f = 0$	$f = 10^{-4}$	$f = 10^{-3}$	$f = 10^{-2}$
500	0.50	1.2e+05	1.1e+05	8.6e+04	2.7e+04
500	0.63	1.5e+05	1.4e+05	1.1e+05	3.5e+04
500	0.75	1.8e+05	1.7e+05	1.4e+05	4.4e+04
1000	0.50	2.3e+05	2.2e+05	1.4e+05	3.0e+04
1000	0.63	3.0e+05	2.8e+05	1.8e+05	4.0e+04
1000	0.75	3.6e+05	3.4e+05	2.2e+05	5.0e+04
5000	0.50	1.2e+06	8.6e+05	2.5e+05	3.3e+04
5000	0.63	1.5e+06	1.1e+06	3.4e+05	4.4e+04
5000	0.75	1.8e+06	1.3e+06	4.2e+05	5.6e+04

composite (higher $dn_{\text{eff}}/dn_{\text{pore}}$), the accompanying absorption loss (finite $\kappa = \text{Im}(n_{\text{eff}})$) reduces Q_{total} more strongly, so even trace amounts of nanoparticles degrade performance, with the FOM falling monotonically as loading increases. In our sweep, the best doped case occurs at the smallest nonzero fraction ($f_{\text{opt}} = 0.0010$), and it still underperforms the bare sensor ($f = 0$).

A subtle point is that much of the optoplasmonic-WGM literature is optimized for *reactive* single-entity readout with a small number of plasmonic antennas, where the central resource is the localized hotspot field and the readout is dominated by discrete step-like events rather than an equilibrium refractometric figure of merit. [11] In that regime, additional observables beyond the resonance shift are often informative; for example, linewidth changes can directly report optical losses (absorption and scattering) introduced by the analyte or the plasmonic structure. [11] By contrast, in passive refractometric sensing the attainable resolution scales strongly with the cavity linewidth (and thus with Q), so absorption-driven Q degradation must be treated on equal footing with any sensitivity/overlap gain when assessing volumetric loading in porous resonators. [11]

This constitutes a **design rule under the model assumptions** used throughout this work: (i) passive-cavity operation (no gain compensation), (ii) refractometric readout quantified by $\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$, (iii) visible-wavelength operation where noble metals exhibit appreciable loss, and (iv) dilute volumetric inclusions described by effective-medium homogenization. Within this scope, the optimal strategy for maximizing passive refractometric FOM is to avoid plasmonic volumetric doping and rely on the bare mesoporous resonator.

Volumetric optoplasmonics can nevertheless remain useful when the objective is *not* maximum equilibrium FOM. In particular, nanoparticle loading in a mesoporous shell can introduce transport- and binding-limited dynamics that imprint time-dependent spectral signatures encoding kinetic information even when the equilibrium FOM is degraded (see Supplementary Material for a detailed diffusion-binding model).

Moreover, architectures that compensate loss (e.g., active/gain-assisted cavities [11]) or geometries/material choices that reduce κ may shift the trade-off. Anisotropic nanoparticles (e.g., nanorods) with modified polarizability-to-loss ratio [24, 28] therefore represent a promising direction for future work.

An important outlook is that the trade-off quantified here is specific to *passive* cavities. The Perspective literature emphasizes that passive WGM sensors face fundamental noise limits (e.g., thermorefractive noise) and that active WGM microlasers can provide markedly narrower effective linewidths above threshold, enabling self-heterodyne/beatnote readout and reduced sensitivity to common-mode fluctuations. [11] In this sense, gain-assisted or microlaser architectures offer a plausible route to partially compensate loss channels that are detrimental in passive operation, and therefore may shift the balance between plasmonic overlap enhancement and absorption loss in future volumetric designs. [11]

Based on these results, we propose the following guidelines:

- **Passive visible refractometric sensing:** use the bare porous resonator ($f = 0$); volumetric plasmonic doping reduces $\text{FOM} = S \times Q_{\text{total}}$.
- If plasmonic functionality is required for a different modality (e.g., SERS) or for time-resolved kinetic fingerprinting, keep the loading in the trace regime ($f \lesssim 10^{-3}$) to limit absorption-induced Q degradation.
- To mitigate loss, prefer lower-loss spectral windows (e.g., longer wavelengths) and/or lower-loss nanoparticle designs (e.g., dielectric coatings), and quantify κ explicitly rather than assuming “hotspots” imply improved FOM.
- When temporal signatures are the primary goal, moderate loading can be acceptable even at reduced equilibrium FOM, provided the application benefits from the added kinetic information.

4 Conclusion

We developed a quantitative framework to evaluate volumetric optoplasmonic sensing in mesoporous, passive-cavity WGM resonators by combining (i) an optoplasmonic coupling description built on the Foreman–Vollmer T-matrix approach with a continuous-density (sum-to-integral) approximation for nanoparticles distributed throughout the mesoporous shell, and (ii) a two-step effective-medium model (Bruggeman + Maxwell–Garnett) that yields the complex effective refractive index of the nanoparticle-doped porous composite, including absorption losses. [5, 16–19] Anchored to the experimentally realized mesoporous hollow silica microcapsule platform, this model enables a direct and self-consistent computation of refractive-index sensitivity, absorption-limited Q degradation, and the resulting figure of merit $\text{FOM} = S Q_{\text{total}}$. [15]

For passive refractometric operation in the visible (645 nm), we find a clear and practically relevant outcome: within the assumptions of our model, the introduction of plasmonic nanoparticles, even at minimal volume fractions, consistently lowers the achievable FOM relative to the bare mesoporous resonator. In particular, gold produces a strong degradation (a 41% reduction in FOM even at the lowest loading considered, $f = 10^{-3}$, in our sweep), while silver leads to a smaller but still negative change (13% at the same loading). This behavior reflects a fundamental trade-off in passive optoplasmonics at visible wavelengths, where the modest increase in sensitivity enabled by volumetric loading is outweighed by absorption-induced Q reduction. [12, 14, 22, 23]

Beyond equilibrium performance, nanoparticle loading in a mesoporous shell can couple optical response to transport by introducing diffusion-limited access to internal hotspots, yielding time-dependent WGM shifts that may encode kinetic information. Thus, while plasmonic doping is not advantageous for maximizing passive-cavity refractometric FOM in the visible, it may still be useful when time-resolved kinetic fingerprinting (rather than maximal equilibrium resolution) is the primary objective.

Overall, our results establish a simple design rule for mesoporous passive-cavity WGM refractometric sensors operating in the visible: the bare mesoporous resonator remains the optimal configuration for FOM-limited sensing, and plasmonic inclusions should be avoided unless one explicitly targets time-dependent signatures or adopts alternative architectures (e.g., gain-compensated/active cavities or operation in lower-loss spectral windows) [12, 14]. The present model treats the shell as a homogeneous effective medium; full-wave FEM simulations (e.g. FDTD/FEM) could in principle resolve individual nanoparticle near-fields, but are not expected to alter the sign of the FOM trade-off established here, since this is governed by the macroscopic imaginary part of the effective index rather than local field detail. The predicted FOM degradation invites direct experimental verification using the hollow mesoporous microcapsule platform [15] with controlled nanoparticle infiltration. Finally, our results point toward a promising direction for future work: dielectric high-index nanoparticles (e.g., silicon, germanium) that can achieve strong field confinement without Ohmic losses, which may enable the volumetric enhancement predicted by Eq. (11) without the catastrophic Q degradation associated with plasmonic metals. [12, 14]

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